

INFORMATIVE DESCRIPTION ON INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Manaswi N.*², Satish Kumar B. P.¹, Ashik P. T.², Thasvin U. R.², Madhu M.²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Sri Adichunchanagiri College of Pharmacy, B.G Nagara-571418, India.

²Pharm D Graduate, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Sri Adichunchanagiri College of Pharmacy, B.G Nagara-571418, India.

Article Received on
14 June 2024,

Revised on 04 July 2024,
Accepted on 25 July 2024

DOI: 10.20959/wjpr202415-33364

***Corresponding Author**

Manaswi N.

Pharm Graduate,

Department of Pharmacy

Practice, Sri

Adichunchanagiri College

of Pharmacy, B.G Nagara-

571418, India.

ABSTRACT

This informed consent form provides a clear and comprehensive overview of the [procedure/study/treatment], including its purpose, potential risks and benefits, and the responsibilities of both the participant/patient and the researcher/clinician. By signing this form, participants/patients acknowledge that they have read and understood the information provided, and give their voluntary consent to participate. This form serves as a critical component of ethical research and clinical practice, ensuring that individuals are fully informed and able to make autonomous decisions about their participation. It also helps to establish trust and transparency between researchers/clinicians and participants/patients, and demonstrates compliance with regulatory requirements and ethical guidelines.

KEYWORDS: Consent, Participation, Voluntary, Information.

INTRODUCTION

A key concept in many domains, such as research, healthcare, and data collecting, is informed consent, which guarantees that people are aware of the goals, dangers, and advantages of a given course of action or therapy.^[1] A consent form, which contains this information, is an essential tool for enabling people to make decisions about their own bodies, data, and wellbeing.^[2]

Consent forms are essential because they are grounded on ethical precepts like beneficence, non-maleficence, and respect for autonomy.^[3] From the Nuremberg Code (1947) to the

Helsinki Declaration (2013), the idea of informed consent has changed over time, with a focus on the necessity of voluntary and informed permission.^[4,5] Informed consent guarantees that patients are aware of their diagnosis, available treatments, and any consequences. It is crucial for patient-centered care in the healthcare industry.^[6]

According to the Belmont Report (1979), informed consent is essential for safeguarding study participants' rights and dignity.^[7] Assuring that participants are aware of the goals, dangers, and advantages of the research as well as their freedom to withdraw at any moment requires informed consent, which is emphasised in the report.^[7] Ensuring that individuals are aware of how their personal information will be used and safeguarded throughout data collection requires informed consent.^[8]

Strong consent procedures are essential, as evidenced by recent worries about privacy, autonomy, and exploitation.^[9] It is more important than ever to make sure that people understand exactly what they are consenting to, due to the growing complexity of medical treatments, research protocols, and data collection techniques.^[10] Moreover, new rules and regulations like the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) have increased the bar for consent standards.^[11,12]

This review article will investigate the importance of permission forms, including their background, moral foundations, and legal environment. We will look at the fundamentals of informed consent, talk about particular issues for populations who are more susceptible, and showcase best practices for creating and putting into place efficient consent procedures. Our goal is to encourage a culture of openness, dignity, and patient-centered care by highlighting the significance of consent forms.

- Informed consent is not an ancient concept, neither does it have a long medical history. The phrase initially arose in 1957, but it wasn't until roughly 1972 that the idea was the subject of substantial debate.

- A few percent of physicians in the 18th and 19th centuries championed patient rights to information but not informed consent. Rather, they desired that people possess enough knowledge to comprehend the advice of their doctors and, as a result, be inspired to follow it.

- Early in the 20th century, courts did not hesitate to punish the frequently heinous behaviour of physicians by use forceful language and broad ideas. Later cases, in which the behaviour of the physicians was less extreme, used the same wording as precedent. Instead of straying

from the language of self-determination, the law progressively relied on this reasoning as its central tenet as the informed-consent doctrine evolved and issues became more complicated.

- The concept of informed consent was originally introduced to the medical profession by the developing legal doctrine of informed consent. The legal concept known as "the doctrine of informed consent" is frequently used interchangeably with informed consent. Both attorneys and doctors became aware of informed consent in the second half of the 20th century due to a remarkable series of incidents.

Ethical basis

The significance of consent forms is justified ethically by a number of fundamental ideas. In the first place, informed consent fosters confidence in medical practice, which is necessary for providing quality care.^[1] Second, consent forms uphold patients' right to self-determination regarding their own health and bodies.^[2] Third, informed consent ensures that patients are aware of the possible hazards as well as the advantages of any treatments or procedures, which helps prevent injury.^[3] Consent forms, fourth, ensure that patients are properly informed about their care and foster transparency in the medical field.^[4] Fifth, by exhibiting respect for patients' autonomy and rights, gaining informed permission can help healthcare practitioners avoid legal problems.^[5] Sixth, consent forms promote patient participation in their care, which improves health

outcomes^[6] Finally, informed consent aligns with ethical principles like respect for persons, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice.^[7]

Key elements of informed consent from

Clear purpose

The purpose of an informed consent form is to ensure that participants understand and agree to participate in a research study, medical treatment or other activities that may affect their well-being.^[1,2] The purpose of the informed consent form includes.^[1,2,3,4]

- Describing the general purpose of the study.
- Providing an explanation of the procedures and treatments.
- Describing the potential risks and benefits.
- Explaining the rights and responsibilities of the individual.
- Outlining the confidentiality and privacy measures in place.
- Explaining the option to withdraw or refuse participation.
- Providing contact information for questions or concerns.

- Assuring that the participant understands that their participation is voluntary and that they may refuse to answer any questions or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Risks and benefits

Informed consent documents for clinical studies should disclose all reasonably foreseeable risks and benefits.^[1,2] Risks and benefits of informed consent forms include.^[3,1,2]

- Risk

Health risks, for example, should be specified with frequency numbers.

Only fourteen forms (14) indicated that a cure would even be a potential advantage, whereas the majority (181) identified death as a risk.

The majority (229) said there was an unknown danger and that there could be serious or long-term consequences (224).

- Benefits

Health benefits should be specified at least by mentioning their outcomes.

The chance and magnitude of any health benefits were never stated, and only 45% of informed consent forms included the results of any health benefits that were discussed. The 172 informed consent documents varied significantly in a number of ways regarding the risk-benefit analysis.^[1,2]

Right to withdrawal

- Right to withdraw: Participants have the right to withdraw from a research study at any time without penalty or loss of benefits.

- Voluntary participation: Participants are made aware that their participation is completely voluntary and that they can end it whenever they choose.

- No waiver of legal rights: Withdrawing from a study does not waive any legal claims, rights, or remedies.

- Notification: If a participant wants to stop participating, they should let the study team know.

- Reasons for withdrawal: Participants may be asked for the reasons for withdrawal, but are not required to provide them.

- Consequences of withdrawal: Participants are made aware of the potential loss of benefits or the inability to receive specific therapies should they choose to withdraw.

- Safe discontinuation: Researchers must ensure safe discontinuation of participation and take necessary steps to minimize any potential harm.
- Retention of data: Prior to withdrawal, data may be retained and used by researchers; however, they must make sure the data is de-identified and maintained safely.
- Follow-up activities: Following withdrawal, researchers may carry out follow-up activities, but they will need the participant's extra consent.

Confidentiality

Confidentiality: It is imperative that the informed consent form guarantees the confidentiality of participants' personally identifiable information, allowing access to only authorised workers.

Privacy: Participants' privacy policies should be outlined in the form, along with how anonymity will be preserved through the use of coding, de-identified data, and other techniques.

Data security: The form should outline the precautions taken, including electronic and physical ones, to guarantee the security and integrity of the participants' data.

Disclosure of information: The form should outline the situations in which participants' information may be shared, such as when someone is in danger of harming himself or others or when it's mandated by law.

Access to information: The form should explain who will have access to participants' information and for what purposes.

Storage and retention: The document should outline the methods for data destruction or return as well as the length of time that participant information will be kept on file.

Signature: An informed consent form's signature and date section is an essential component that attests to the participant's comprehension and consent to take part in the medical procedure or research study. Here's what you should know.

***Signature**

- The approval and understanding of the information provided in the informed consent form is indicated by the participant's signature.
- Due to the participant starting the study or therapy, the signature must be collected.

***Date:**

- To verify when consent was received, the date should be included with the participant's signature.

- For record-keeping and auditing purposes, the date is crucial.

Types of consent form

There are several types of informed consent forms, including.

1. **Written Informed Consent Form:** a written consent form that participants physically sign. (1)
2. **Electronic Informed Consent Form (EICF):** A written form in electronic format that is utilised for online research or electronic data gathering. (2)
3. **Oral Informed Consent Form:** used in research (such phone or video interviews) when participants are not needed to sign a written consent form. (3)
4. **Implied Informed Consent Form:** It is suggested that participants have given their consent by their actions taking part in a study or survey, for example. (4)
5. **Expedited Review Informed Consent Form:** used for low-risk research projects like questionnaires and interviews. (5)
6. **Waiver of Informed Consent Form:** used in situations where getting informed permission is impractical or could damage the validity of the study. (6)
7. **Parental or Guardian Informed Consent Form:** used in research involving children when the consent is given on their behalf by parents or guardians. (7)
8. **Assent Form:** Used when combined with parental consent for research involving minors or those with limited comprehension, wherein the subjects provide their assent. (8)

Written consent form

- **Language and reading level:** The language used in the informed consent form should be at the level of a local student in 6th or 8th grade.
- **Logo:** The informed consent form should bear the logo of the study institution, not the WHO symbol.
- **Components:** The informed consent form consists of two parts: the information sheet and the consent certificate.
- **Key questions:** To make sure the participant understands the information being given, important questions should be included in the informed consent form.
- **Electronic signatures:** Electronic signatures are allowed, but they have to abide by all applicable laws and rules, like the FDA's 21 CFR part 11 standards.

To ensure that participants understand the research study and their engagement, keep in mind that informed consent forms are essential.

Informed consent from participants in clinical trials or research studies is obtained via electronic informed consent (EIC) forms. Key information regarding electronic informed consent forms is provided below:

- Definition: The practice of getting participants' informed consent using electronic means such as internet platforms, mobile devices, or electronic data capture systems is known as electronic informed consent. (1)
- Advantages: EIC forms have a number of advantages, such as better data quality, lower expenses, more efficiency, and real-time documentation. (2)
- Regulatory compliance: EIC forms have to be complying with all applicable laws, including the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and the Electronic Signatures in Global and National Commerce Act (ESIGN). (3)
- Best practices: The best practices for completing EIC forms include keeping participant data secure and intact, utilising straightforward language, and including interactive components to aid in participant understanding. (4)
- Examples: Electronic data collection systems utilised in clinical trials, smartphone apps, and online consent platforms are a few examples of EIC forms. (5)

The process of getting informed consent from participants orally, without the use of a written consent form, is known as oral informed consent. The following are important considerations for oral informed consent:

- Definition: A verbal discussion of the research study or clinical trial's risks, benefits, and procedures is known as oral informed consent, and it is followed by the participant's verbal permission to participate. (1)
- Use cases: When participants are not literate or cannot access a written consent form, or when time is of the essence in an emergency, oral informed consent is usually utilised. (2)
- Regulatory compliance: Oral informed consent must comply with relevant regulations, such as the Common Rule (45 CFR 46) and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). (3)
- Best practices: Encouraging participants to ask questions, use straightforward language, and recording the consent procedure in the participant's file are all examples of best practices for oral informed consent. (4)

Implied informed consent is a type of consent that is inferred from a person's actions or behavior, rather than being explicitly stated through a written or oral consent process. Here are some key points about implied informed consent:

- Definition: When someone participates in a study or treatment without expressly giving approval, they are giving implied informed consent. (1)
- Use cases: In circumstances where there is little danger, such surveys, observational studies, or standard medical procedures, implied informed consent is usually used. (2)
- Regulatory compliance: Regulations such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) and the Common Rule (45 CFR 46) must be followed in order for implied informed consent to be valid. (3)
- Best practices: Ensuring that participants are aware of the consequences of their choices, explaining the study or therapy in detail, and recording the consent procedure in the participant's record are all recommended practices for implied informed consent. (4)

For research projects where participants face little risk, an accelerated review informed consent form is utilised. The following are important details about informed consent and accelerated review.

Definition: expedite review for research studies deemed to be minimal risk—that is, if the dangers are no higher than those experienced in everyday life—informed consent is a simplified consent procedure. (1)

Use cases: Expedited review informed consent is typically used for studies such as.

- + Surveys or questionnaires
- + Interviews or focus groups
- + Observational studies
- + Studies using existing data or samples
- + Low-risk interventions or treatments

Regulatory compliance: Expedited review informed consent must comply with relevant regulations, such as the Common Rule (45 CFR 46) and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). (2)

Best practices: Best practices for expedited review informed consent include.

- + Providing succinct and understandable study content
- + Ensuring that participants are aware of the consequences of their involvement
- + Documenting in the participant's file the consent procedure
- + Whenever possible, getting express permission

A form of informed consent utilised for research studies involving minors (those under the age of eighteen) is parental or guardian consent. These are some essential details regarding informed permission from parents or guardians:

Definition: A consent form signed by a parental or guardian granting consent for a minor to take part in a research project is known as parental or guardian informed consent. (1)

Use cases: Parental or guardian informed consent is typically used for studies involving.

- * Minors in educational settings (e.g., schools)
- * Clinical trials or research studies dealing with paediatrics
- * Interviews or questionnaires given to kids
- * Observational research with minors

Regulatory compliance: Consent from parental or guardian that is informed must abide by applicable laws, such as.

- * 45 CFR 46 Subpart D (Protection of Human Subjects: Children)
- * FDA regulations (21 CFR 50 Subpart D)

Best practices: Best practices for parental or guardian informed consent include:

- * Providing succinct and understandable learning information
- * Ensuring that guardians or parents are aware of the consequences of their child's involvement
- * Documenting the consent process in the minor's record
- * Getting the parents' or guardians' express consent

Another kind of informed consent form used for investigations involving minors or people with limited comprehension is the assent form. Here are some essential details regarding consent forms.

Definition: An assent form is a condensed consent form that makes the research project understandable to children or those with impaired comprehension. (1)

Use cases: Assent forms are typically used for studies involving.

- Children from age 7-17
- Individuals that suffer from cognitive abnormalities or developmental problems
- Those with mental health issues that impair their ability to make decisions

Regulatory compliance: Assent forms must comply with relevant regulations, such as.

- 45 CFR 46 Subpart D (Protection of Human Subjects: Children)
- FDA regulations (21 CFR 50 Subpart D)

Best practices: Best practices for assent forms include.

- Making use of straightforward language and explanations
- Avoiding complicated ideas and technical language
- Using pictures or other visual aids to help with comprehension
- Confirming that the participant is aware of the consequences of their involvement

Special populations

When it comes to informed consent, special populations are those who might need additional protections or considerations when taking part in research projects. Here are some important details about informed consent for particular populations.

- Vulnerable populations: Individuals who may be vulnerable to coercion or exploitation, such as:
 - Prisoners (45 CFR 46 Subpart C)
 - Pregnant women (45 CFR 46 Subpart B)
 - Children (45 CFR 46 Subpart D)
 - Individuals with mental disabilities (45 CFR 46 Subpart B)
- Limited English proficiency:
- Low literacy: Individuals who may require simplified consent forms or additional support
- Cognitive impairments: Individuals who may require adapted consent forms or additional support

Regulatory compliance

- 45 CFR 46 (Protection of Human Subjects)
- FDA regulations (21 CFR 50)

Best Practices

- Using clear and simple language
- providing extra assistance or resources when required
- ensuring comprehension and the ability to give consent
- Documenting the consent process

Challenges

- Patients' inadequate understanding of their rights: Patients find it challenging to make educated judgements regarding their participation in research or therapy because they are unaware of their rights.
- Lack of adequate information: Insufficient information provided to patients prevents them from making educated decisions, rendering the consent form void.
- Language barriers: Patients who are illiterate or have poor English ability could find it difficult to understand the permission form.
- Cognitive impairments: People with intellectual disabilities or cognitive impairments might need special consent forms or extra assistance.
- Coercion or undue influence: The consent document may be signed by patients under duress or compulsion, which would violate their right to autonomy.
- Information overload: Too much material on consent forms frequently causes participant weariness and poor comprehension.
- Cultural differences: The informed consent process may be impacted by cultural variations in values, beliefs, and communication methods.
- Power dynamics: The informed consent procedure may be impacted by power imbalances between participants and researchers.
- Electronic consent: Digital permission forms may give rise to privacy and security problems.
- Waiver of consent: Sometimes it's important to waive consent, but this can be a difficult and contentious decision.
- Evolving nature of research: It is challenging to predict all possible dangers or changes because research studies frequently change throughout time.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, informed consent is a crucial concept in various fields, including research, healthcare, and data collection. It ensures that individuals are aware of the purpose, risks, and benefits of a study, treatment, or procedure, and that they provide their voluntary consent to participate. The importance of informed consent is grounded in ethical principles such as respect for autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice. Consent forms are essential tools that facilitate informed decision-making and protect the rights and dignity of individuals. However, challenges such as inadequate understanding, language barriers, cognitive impairments, coercion, and information overload can undermine the informed

consent process. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that consent forms are clear, concise, and culturally sensitive, and that researchers and healthcare professionals are trained to obtain informed consent in a manner that respects the autonomy and dignity of individuals. By prioritizing informed consent, we can promote a culture of transparency, accountability, and patient-centered care.

REFERENCES

1. Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2013). *Principles of biomedical ethics*. Oxford University Press.
2. Appelbaum, P. S., & Grisso, T. (2001). *MacArthur competence assessment tool for treatment (MacCAT-T)*. Sarasota, FL: Professional Resource Press.
3. National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (1979). *The Belmont Report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research*.
4. World Medical Association. (2013). *Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects*.
5. Nuremberg Code. (1947). *Trials of war criminals before the Nuremberg Military Tribunals under Control Council Law No. 10*.
6. American Medical Association. (2019). *Informed consent*.
7. National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (1979). *The Belmont Report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research*.
8. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2013). *OECD guidelines on the protection of privacy and transborder flows of personal data*.
9. Manson, N. C., & O'Neill, O. (2007). *Rethinking informed consent in bioethics*. Cambridge University Press.
10. Berg, J. W., & Appelbaum, P. S. (2001). *Informed consent: Legal theory and clinical practice*. Oxford University Press.
11. European Union. (2018). *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*.
12. State of California. (2018). *California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA)*.
13. A Modern History of Informed Consent and the Role of Key Information. Lydia A Bazzano et al. *Ochsner J*. 2021 Spring
14. *J Prosthodont*, 2022 Jul; 31(6): 464–471. Published online 2022 Mar 8. doi: 10.1111/jopr.13493

15. A Modern History of Informed Consent and the Role of Key Information Lydia A. Bazzano, MD, PhD, MPH, CIP,^{1,2,3} Jaquail Durant, BS,³ and Paula Rhode Brantley, PhD⁴.
16. Beauchamp, T. L., & Childress, J. F. (2013). Principles of biomedical ethics. Oxford University Press.
17. Appelbaum, P. S., & Grisso, T. (2001). MacArthur competence assessment tool for treatment (MacCAT-T). Sarasota, FL: Professional Resource Press.
18. Berg, J. W., & Appelbaum, P. S. (2001). Informed consent: Legal theory and clinical practice. Oxford University Press.
19. National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (1979). The Belmont Report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research.
20. American Medical Association. (2019). Informed consent.
21. Manson, N. C., & O'Neill, O. (2007). Rethinking informed consent in bioethics. Cambridge University Press.
22. World Medical Association. (2013). Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects.
23. <https://www.brandeis.edu/ora/hrpp/special-topics/consent/elements-informed-consent.html>
24. <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/managing-cancer/making-treatment-decisions/informed-consent/what-is-informed-consent.html>
25. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK430827/>
26. https://research.iium.edu.my/irec/?page_id=1168
27. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1740774520971770>
28. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347626882_Details_of_risk-benefit_communication_in_informed_consent_documents_for_phase_III_trials
29. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12501226/>
30. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21105947/>
31. <https://www.unr.edu/research-integrity/human-research/human-research-protection-policy-manual/346-consent-and-early-withdrawal-or-cessation-of-participation>
32. <https://www.ukri.org/councils/esrc/guidance-for-applicants/research-ethics-guidance/consent/>
33. <https://laverne.edu/irb/wp-content/uploads/sites/28/2019/02/GDPR-Consent-for-EEA-Resident-Participants.docx>

34. World Health Organization (WHO). (2017). Guidelines for informed consent in research. Geneva: WHO.
35. National Institutes of Health (NIH). (2020). Informed consent and privacy. Bethesda, MD: NIH.
36. The Belmont Report. (1979). Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research. Washington, D.C.: National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research.
37. American Psychological Association (2017). Ethical principles of psychologists and code of conduct. Washington, DC: APA.
38. Office for Human Research Protections (2020). Expedited review. Washington, D.C.: OHRP.
39. Food and Drug Administration (2019). Informed consent. Silver Spring, MD: FDA.
40. National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (2019). Informed consent and assent. Bethesda, MD: NIH.
41. American Academy of Pediatrics (2019). Informed consent and assent in pediatric research. *Pediatrics*, 143(3), e20190234.
42. Thomson Reuters (2019). Electronic informed consent: A guide to implementing eIC in clinical trials. New York: Thomson Reuters.
43. The Association of Clinical Research Professionals (2019). Electronic informed consent: Best practices and considerations. Nashville, TN: ACRP.
44. Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative (2020). Electronic informed consent: Examples and case studies. Durham, NC: CTTI.
45. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31296111/>
46. <https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13063-020-04969-w>